

ESSENCE AND OBJECTIVES OF PROBABILISTIC MICROBIOLOGY

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8005627>

Mashkhura Sadikova

*Assistant, Bukhara Institute of Engineering and Technology,
Republic of Uzbekistan, Bukhara*

Abstract.

The article discusses the essence and tasks of probabilistic microbiology for predicting the behavior of microbes in the environment of food raw materials and finished products. Various modeling options in this direction are discussed.

Key words.

microbes, pathogens, food safety, probabilistic microbiology, modeling.

СУЩНОСТЬ И ЗАДАЧИ ВЕРОЯТНОСТНОЙ МИКРОБИОЛОГИИ

Садикова Машхура Идиллоевна

*ассистент,
Бухарский инженерно-технологический институт,
Республика Узбекистан, г. Бухара*

Аннотация.

В статье рассматривается сущность и задачи вероятностной микробиологии для предсказания поведения микробов в среде пищевого сырья и готового продукта. Обсуждаются различные варианты моделирования в данном направлении.

Ключевые слова.

микробы, патогены, пищевая безопасность, вероятностная микробиология, моделирование.

Introduction. Among the microorganism found in food and raw materials, only a small part are pathogens that cause certain diseases. A working knowledge of these microbes is essential for food safety [1]. The development of methods for detecting and quantifying pathogens and their toxins, such as microscopic fungi and the aflatoxins they produce, is central to this. Microbial testing and information can be used to predict the possible emergence of pathogens. This issue is dealt with by probabilistic microbiology, and consideration of its essence and tasks is the purpose of this article.

Results and its discussion.

1. Interaction between microorganisms.

The relationship between microorganisms in BC is not considered in most probabilistic models, and only a few of the published articles deal with the modeling of microbial interactions in BC. Recently, more attention has been paid to interactions in probabilistic models, especially those that describe the effect of lactic acid bacteria on the behavior of foodborne pathogens and viruses [2]. A model [1] has been developed that combines the growth and metabolic activity of lactic acid bacteria, a group of microbes that are often used as a starter culture for fermentable PNs, such as lactic acid products or fermented meat products. In PP, lactic acid bacteria is used as a protective culture – or biopreservative – against pathogens and damaging organisms. This model [1]. It is based on the formation of lactic acid by lactic acid bacteria. The transition from the exponential phase to the stationary phase, which is growth inhibition, could be modeled by the concentration of undissociated lactic acid and acidification of the medium. Following this, [2] a per-culture model based on the same theory describing growth was proposed. Mono- and co-cultures of *Yersinia enterocolitica*, a pathogen, together with *Lactobacillus*, a lactic acid bacterium. Pathogen inhibition could be modeled by lactic acid production by this bacterium (*Lactobacillires*).

2. The structure of the food product.

Over the past decade, a large number of plausible models for microbial growth have been developed. Many of them do not take into account the variability of microbial growth depending on environmental conditions. In a homogeneous environment, like broth and fluid PPs, this variability does not change or may be negligible. However, in structured PNs (heterogeneous) growth-determining factors such as T and pH, and thus microbial growth itself, may be highly dependent on position in PP. Moreover, due to the solid structure of PP, microorganisms could grow strongly in colonies, in which the value and effects of interaction play a more important role compared to fluid products. Dacks [3] applied a coupled approach to stimulate the *Lactobacillus* contamination behavior of the mixture. and *E. coli* in PP with a very low diffusion coefficient, which is inherent in solid PP. He showed a picture of education, making possible the global coexistence of both species, which is not inherent in a homogeneous liquid medium. Recently, a model has been developed [3], which describes 2 phenomena: 1) local evolution of biomass and 2) transfer of biomass through the medium. In this situation, the probabilistic model is based on experiments with solid PP safety broth.

3. Variety of natural strains.

Naturally encountered strains of PP pathogens, as well as spoiling microbes, differ in their attitude to stress conditions [4]. Begot compared the growth parameters of 58 *List.monoc.* and 8 *L.innoc.* strains at various combinations of pH (5.6 and 7.0), temperature (10 and 37°C) and water activity (0.96 and 1.0). Wide variation between different strains was described under the same conditions, especially for the lag phase. With one combination ($a_w = 0.96$; $t = 10^{\circ}\text{C}$, $\text{pH} = 7.0$), the minimum lag phase was 3.9 h, while the maximum lag phase was estimated at 97.9 h. Under the same conditions, the maximum time generation was 2.3 times the minimum generation time. In addition, strains showing long initial population generation times do not show the maximum lag time. Cluster analysis showed that the group of fast growing strains under all conditions were mostly complex strains isolated from industrial sites. These results show the difficulty in choosing the strain on which the probabilistic model is based. If a fast growing strain is considered, then the model always predicts a shorter lag time and slower growth rate than what is found for most strains, always providing safe growth calculations. On the other hand, the question may arise about the reality of the predictions made by the developed models with rapidly growing strains. The ideal model should also quantify the uncertainty of predictions caused by the heterogeneity of natural strains.

4. Simulation of the lag phase.

Heterogeneity (variability) of the population lag phase, i.e. the time it takes for bacteria to adapt to new environmental conditions before they begin to multiply is an important source of variability in the exposure assessment stage when risk assessment for *L.monoc* is carried out. Studies on modeling the behavior of bacteria in PP have repeatedly shown that the lag phase is more difficult to model than the specific growth time. Pre-adaptation to growth conditions can greatly reduce the lag time, and the magnitude of this effect is difficult to predict. Likewise, the level of the inoculum has an important influence on the lag phase. It turned out that the variability in the timing of detection of *L.monoc.* increases when a low level of inoculum is applied when dealing with constant inoculum levels, an increase in variation can be observed when a more saline medium is applied [5]. Therefore, when dealing with actual low levels of pathogen inoculum, such as *L. monoc.*, high variability can be expected in the lag phase of the population, especially when variable growth inhibition conditions are applied. High initial bacterial density is theoretically associated with high fasting, including at least one cell in a suitable physiological state for immediate growth, with only a limited lag time for

adjustment [1]. The individual approach to the cell is therefore in an adequate quantification of such distributions. Even if the inoculum effect is minimized, it is still difficult to get a clear picture of the lag time variation path as a function of environmental conditions. Various studies have shown a relationship between lag time and growth rate, but there is no universal confirmation of this relationship. A clear understanding of the mechanisms of action of stress conditions on the microbial cell, as well as on culture adaptation systems, may lead to a better prediction of the lag phase. Until then, however, a lag phase should not be ruled out when predicting spoilage or microbial safety of PP, but careful interpretation of probabilistic models is necessary. 5. Modeling the behavior of microbes that cause spoilage of PP.

Because Since criteria for storage times and conditions for most PPs are established by combining criteria for PP pathogens and porosity-causing microorganisms, mathematical models will be useful in predicting the behavior of major groups of damaging microorganisms. The development of suitable models for such microbes has received little attention. The development of mathematical models that predict microbial spoilage of PP usually takes into account the product and/or the specifics of production, which are very limited. However, in recent years, great interest has been paid to the study of por-i prediction [5].

6. Work with unrealistic probabilistic modeling.

When working with predictions, unrealistic assumptions are sometimes made. This is mostly the case for black box models that do not contain mechanistic elements, have unrealistic high R² values, but impossible results because unrealistic curves or even negative lag phases or negative growth rates may occur. A novel approach for 2 models was developed [6] involving microbial knowledge in a black box model.

Conclusion. The use of predictive models can provide information quickly and is therefore important to obtain the real value and usefulness of these models. However, it is important to emphasize that their use cannot replace the microbial analysis of samples or the technical skills of an experienced microbiologist. This can be interpreted as follows: "The model is a good discussion partner, giving good ideas, guiding you in the right direction, but like any discussion partners is not always right." These models should be considered as one of the decision-making tools active in the field of PP and are in a position to consolidate their decisions. Probabilistic food microbiology finds various applications [7].

BIBLIOGRAPHY:

1. Vereecken K.M. Ital.2012 "Analyse practical implementation of a model for combined growth and methalite production of lacti acid baceria "Jut.Jonck.Food Microbiol., 93,333
2. Vereecken K.M. Ital.2013 "A model for lactic acid - induced ingibition of ver. enter. in mono-and co-culture with.Lact. Sak., Food Microbiol., 30, 301
3. Dens E.J. etal. "On the impotance of taking space into account when modeling microbial competiton in structured foods" Math. Comput. Simulat 201, 73 (16), 209
4. Begot C. et al. 2017, "Variabilrty of the response of 66 List. Monoc. And List inn. Strains to disserent growth condition" Food Microbiol., 34, 506
5. Robinson T.P. et al. "The effect inocudem size on the lag phase L.monoc." Jnt.J.Food Microbiol., 2011, 90, 103
6. Geeraerd A.H. et al. "Develapment or novel modelly approach for seeondary in predictive microbiolody incorpora tion of microboiologrcal knowledge in block bax polynomial modelling" 2014, Jnt. J. Food Microbiol 131, 222
7. Садикова М. И., Касимова Н. А. К вопросу оценки химической безопасности пищевых продуктов //Universum: химия и биология. 2021. №. 6-2.С. 25-28.
8. Мухамадиев Б.Т., Садикова М. И. Применение электромагнитного поля низкой частоты (эмп нч) в производстве растительных ингредиентов //Universum: химия и биология. 2020. №. 11-2 (77). С. 34-36.
9. Органическое производство пищевых продуктов Садикова М., Касымова Н Scientife Bullettin of NamSU - Научный вестник NamDU Ilmiy Axborotnomasi. 2022 1-сон №103-108
10. Садикова М. И., Мухамадиев Б. Т. Использование плодоовощных криопорошков в пищевой технологии //Universum: химия и биология. - 2021. - №. 4. - С. 46-49.
11. Садикова М. И., Мухамадиев Б. Т. ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЕ КРИОГЕННЫХ ПОРОШКОВ, ОБОГАЩЕННЫХ СО2-ЭКСТРАКТАМИ В ПРОИЗВОДСТВЕ ПИЩЕВЫХ ПРОДУКТОВ //Universum: химия и биология. - 2020. - №. 12-2 (78). - С. 13-15.
12. Садикова М., Туробов Ж. ПРОИЗВОДСТВО ЦЕЛЛЮЛОЗЫ И БУМАГИ //Академические исследования в современной науке. - 2023. - Т. 2. - №. 11. - С. 170-174.

13. Садикова М. И. и др. КАТАЛИТИЧЕСКАЯ ОЧИСТКА ГАЗОВ //ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ НАУКА И ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ ИДЕИ В МИРЕ. – 2023. – Т. 20. – №. 1. – С. 43-47.

14. Садикова М. И. и др. МИНЕРАЛЬНОЕ И ОРГАНИЧЕСКОЕ СЫРЬЕ //ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ НАУКА И ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ ИДЕИ В МИРЕ. – 2023. – Т. 20. – №. 1. – С. 51-55.

15. Садикова М. И. СВЕРХКРИТИЧЕСКАЯ ХРОМАТОГРАФИЯ (СКФХ) ЭКСТРАКТОВ ЦВЕТКОВ ДЖИДЫ И ЛИСТЬЕВ ЩЕЛКОВИЦЫ //Главный редактор. – 2022. – С. 62.

16. Bobir O., Mashhura S., Islom B. TECHNOLOGY OF OBTAINING EFFECTIVE CORROSION INHIBITORS IN THE OIL AND GAS INDUSTRY //Universum: технические науки. – 2022. – №. 1-3 (94). – С. 85-87.

17. Шарипов М. З. и др. Influence of hexagonal symmetry stresses on domain structure and magnetization process of FeVO₃ single crystal //Eurasian Physical Technical Journal. – 2020. – Т. 17. – №. 1 (33). – С. 65-72.

18. Атоев Э. Х. Исследование взаимодействия солей хрома и цинка с различными органическими реагентами //Консолидация интеллектуальных ресурсов как фундамент развития современной науки. – 2021. – С. 324-330.

19. Атоев Э. Х. ТЕРМИЧЕСКИЕ ПРЕВРАЩЕНИЯ АМОРФНОГО ГИДРОКСИДА ЖЕЛЕЗА //Прогрессивные технологии и процессы. – 2018. – С. 23-24.

20. Атоев Э. Х., Гафурова Г. А. Рафинирование и экстракция семян тыквы сверхкритической углекислотой //Universum: технические науки. – 2020. – №. 5-2 (74). – С. 26-28.

21. Атоев Э. Х. ГЕТЕРОЦИКЛИЧЕСКИЕ ОКСИАЗОСОЕДИНЕНИЯ КАК АНАЛИТИЧЕСКИЕ РЕАГЕНТЫ //Universum: химия и биология. – 2021. – №. 3-2 (81). – С. 4-6.

22. Атоев Э. Х. Строение и свойства внутрикомплексных соединений 8-меркаптохинолина (тиооксина) и его производных //Universum: химия и биология. – 2020. – №. 10-2 (76). – С. 29-32.

23. Атоев Э. Х. СОВРЕМЕННЫЕ ПРЕДСТАВЛЕНИЯ О МЕХАНИЗМЕ ОБРАЗОВАНИЯ СОЕДИНЕНИЯ С АНТИПИРИНОМ И ЕГО ПРОИЗВОДНЫМИ //Universum: химия и биология. – 2021. – №. 10-2 (88). – С. 42-43.

24. Атоев Э. Х. ИССЛЕДОВАНИЕ РЕАКЦИЙ О, О-ДИОКСИАЗОСОЕДИНЕНИЙ //Universum: химия и биология. – 2022. – №. 9-2 (99). – С. 35-37.

25. Атоев Э. Х. ХЕМИЛЮМИНЕСЦЕНТНЫЕ КАТАЛИТИЧЕСКИЕ РЕАКЦИИ ЛЮЦИГЕНИНА С ПЕРЕКИСЬЮ ВОДОРОДА //Universum: химия и биология. – 2022. – №. 3-2 (93). – С. 7-9.

26. Атоев Э. Х., Рамазонов Б. Г. Аналитические Возможности Нового Органического Реагента Сульфохрома // " ONLINE-CONFERENCES" PLATFORM. – 2021. – С. 321-323.

27. Атоев Э. Х. Исследование диффузии ацетона в смеси диацетата целлюлозы с поли-2-метил-5-винилпиридином методом сорбции //Universum: химия и биология. – 2020. – №. 2 (68). – С. 91-94.

28. Атоев Э. Х. ЭЛЕКТРОННОЕ СТРОЕНИЕ АНТИПИРИНА С И ЕГО КОМПЛЕКСОВ С ЛАНТАНОМ //IJTIMOIY FANLARDA INNOVASIYA ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI. – 2022. – Т. 2. – №. 2. – С. 108-110.